

Study of Hydrocarbons Metering Issues in Algerian Fields under the New Law Context

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Abstract : Since the advent of the law 86/14 concerning the exploitation of the national territory by foreign companies in partnership with the Algerian oil and gas company, the problem of hydrocarbons metering in the sharing production come out. More generally, good management counting hydrocarbons can provide data on the production wells, the field and the reservoir for medium and long term planning, particularly in the context of the management and field development. In this work, we are interested in the transactional metering which is a very delicate and crucial period in the current context of the new hydrocarbon's law characterized by assets system between the various activities of Sonatrach and its foreign partners. After a state of the art on hydrocarbons metering devices in Algeria and elsewhere, we will decline the advantages and disadvantages of each system, and then we describe the problem to try to reach an optimal solution.

Keywords : transactional metering, flowmeter orifice, heat flow, Sonatrach

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